

POLITICAL SCIENCES

POLITICAL ACTIONS AND INTERNATIONAL ENGAGEMENTS OF THE VERKHOVNA RADA OF UKRAINE SINCE THE 2022 RUSSIAN-UKRAINIAN WAR: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The Russian-Ukrainian War that erupted on February 24, 2022, had a profound impact on Ukraine's political landscape, leading the Verkhovna Rada to undertake various political actions and international engagements. This research article provides a detailed analysis of the Parliament's legislative activities, foreign policy endeavors, and its pursuit of European integration since the onset of the conflict. Additionally, the study examines the prominence of "Poland" and the "USA" in political speeches during different parliamentary sessions. Through a systematic review of the Verkhovna Rada's actions, this research highlights Ukraine's commitment to countering armed aggression and its aspirations for EU membership.

Keywords: Verkhovna Rada, Ukraine, Russo-Ukrainian War, European integration, International engagements, Legislative activities, Foreign policy

Introduction: The 2022 Russian-Ukrainian War thrust Ukraine into a state of crisis, with Russian aggression threatening the country's territorial integrity and sovereignty. In response to the invasion, the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, the country's supreme legislative body, assumed a central role in implementing measures to counter the armed aggression and solidify Ukraine's position on the international stage. This research article aims to comprehensively analyze the political actions and international engagements of the Verkhovna Rada since the outbreak of the Russian-Ukrainian War, focusing on legislative activities, foreign policy endeavors, and the Parliament's commitment to European integration.

Legislative Activities: Since February 24, 2022, the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine has exhibited remarkable legislative productivity, reflecting its dedication to addressing the challenges posed by the Russian invasion. With an extensive agenda comprising 825 issues, the Parliament adopted 384 laws, out of which approximately 100 were directly aimed at countering the aggression[4]. These legislative measures encompassed a wide range of areas, from national security and defense to humanitarian assistance and economic stability. Notably, the Parliament also passed nine statements and 24 appeals to the international community, emphasizing the urgency of addressing Russia's aggression.

In the field of European integration, the Verkhovna Rada has played a crucial role in advancing Ukraine's path towards EU membership. It adopted 39 laws specifically related to European integration and laid the foundation for further progress by approving 31 bills. Of particular significance was the Parliament's adherence to the recommendations of the European Commission, ensuring the implementation of laws that align with EU standards and regulations[5].

Foreign Policy Engagements: Understanding the significance of international support in countering Russian aggression, the leadership of the Verkhovna Rada actively engaged in diplomatic efforts on multiple fronts. High-level visits to European and international countries sought to rally support for Ukraine's cause, focusing on critical issues such as the country's bid for EU and NATO membership, the establishment of a special tribunal for Russian war criminals, compensation for damages, and the expulsion of Russia from international organizations.

Throughout the year of martial law, the Chairman of the Verkhovna Rada, Ruslan Stefanchuk, undertook 14 official visits, participating in numerous meetings, addressing national parliaments, and attending international conferences. These efforts underscored Ukraine's commitment to seeking global cooperation and solidarity against the aggressor.

World leaders reciprocated Ukraine's resilience with unwavering support. During the full-scale invasion, the Verkhovna Rada received 26 visits from heads of national parliaments and their deputies, as well as 28 delegations from national parliaments and international parliamentary organizations. The influx of foreign representatives addressing the Ukrainian Parliament highlighted the international community's recognition of Ukraine's struggle against the brutal Russian aggression.

Mentions of "Poland" and "USA" in Political Speeches: An analysis of parliamentary sessions during three distinct periods shed light on Ukraine's evolving priorities in international relations. During the 7th session [1] (April 24, 2022, to August 31, 2022) of the 9th convocation, "Poland" was mentioned 158 times, while the "USA" was mentioned 30 times. In the subsequent 8th session [2] (September 1, 2022, to January 31,

2023), "Poland" was mentioned 20 times, and the "USA" 33 times. Finally, in the ongoing 9th session [3]

(February 1, 2023, to May 10, 2023), "Poland" was mentioned 25 times, and the "USA" 19 times.

Fig.1 Parliament of Ukraine: speeches mentioning "Poland"

The variation in mentions of "Poland" and the "USA" may reflect shifting diplomatic priorities and the evolving geopolitical landscape amid the conflict. It is evident that Ukraine's interactions with neighboring

countries and global powers significantly influenced the focus of its political speeches during different phases of the Russian-Ukrainian War.

Fig.2 Parliament of Ukraine: speeches mentioning "USA"

Fig.3 Parliament of Ukraine: speeches mentioning "Poland" and "USA" 7th, 8th, 9th sessions

Conclusions: The Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine has displayed a robust commitment to countering Russian aggression and advancing European integration since the outbreak of the 2022 Russian-Ukrainian War. Its legislative endeavors demonstrate a concerted effort to address the challenges posed by the conflict, promote democratic values, and align national laws with EU standards. The Parliament's active engagement in foreign policy has garnered substantial international support, reaffirming Ukraine's resilience and determination in the face of adversity.

Throughout this research article, we have witnessed the Verkhovna Rada's pivotal role in shaping Ukraine's political landscape and its pursuit of international cooperation. Ukraine's diplomatic efforts and interactions with other nations have been instrumental in reinforcing its position on the global stage.

As the Russian-Ukrainian War continues to unfold, the Verkhovna Rada's actions will continue to shape Ukraine's trajectory, reinforcing its commitment to democracy, sovereignty, and international cooperation. By analyzing the Parliament's legislative activities, foreign policy engagements, and mentions of other nations in political speeches, we gain valuable insights

into Ukraine's response to the crisis and its aspirations for a more secure and integrated future.

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